

THEORETICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL BASES OF VOCATIONAL GUIDANCE WORK OF A PSYCHOLOGIST AT SCHOOL

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Annotation: One of the key professional activities of a psychologist in an educational institution of secondary education is, in particular, career guidance work in all its dimensions and formats. The high level of professionalism of this work presupposes a systematic reliance on the fundamental theoretical and psychological foundations of its practical implementation.

Key words: psychology, psychologist, secondary school, schoolchildren, psychologist's professional activity.

Introduction. The school psychologist carries out systematic monitoring of the professional interests and inclinations of schoolchildren, professionally shows their readiness for profile and professional self-determination through the implementation of appropriate psychodiagnostic examinations of schoolchildren and their parents, conducts psychotraining classes on career guidance for schoolchildren that correspond to psychology, periodically assists the class teacher in analyzing and evaluating interests and inclinations of schoolchildren, forms and regularly replenishes a database of schoolchildren on professional psychodiagnostics [1, 2].

Also, a school psychologist should be well versed in the peculiarities of the national labor market, professional offers of higher education institutions, have the skills of both individual and group psychological counseling on career guidance and know the basics of professional orientation as such [3]. But even this is not enough - in different situations it is important to choose the necessary individual

approach to the student, only capable of providing the optimal practical result [5, 6, 7]. The choice of a specific approach depends on the request of the student or parents, the situation of career guidance, and the student's personal characteristics. To date, a practical psychologist in high school in his career guidance work identifies and uses four teretiko-conceptual approaches to career guidance work at school, namely:

- information;
- diagnostic and consulting;
- developing;
- activating [8, 9, 10].

Consider the first so-called informational approach. The key goal of this approach to career guidance at school is to provide a variety of reliable information to schoolchildren about modern professions, educational institutions and organizations that provide jobs, about the labor market and how to plan their professional career [11, 12, 13]. Examples of the implementation of this approach to career guidance work are: educational exhibitions, professional job fairs, meetings with specialists, representatives of various universities and social organizations, institutions, institutions, presentations, seminars on career guidance topics; guides, articles, videos.

The diagnostic and consulting approach is carried out in order to establish the student's compliance with a particular type of activity by comparing his individual characteristics and requirements for professions. Examples of its application are psychological interview, psychological interview and psychological questioning; career guidance individual psychological counseling; career guidance psychodiagnostic tests and complexes of psychodiagnostic testing that assess the professional potential of the subjects and professionally important qualities [14, 15].

As for the developmental approach, its main goal is to develop in schoolchildren a variety of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for mastering a particular profession, for successful employment [16, 17].

And, accordingly, an activating approach is used to purposefully form in secondary school students a conscious internal readiness for independent and scientifically based construction of their professional and general life path [18]. This approach, as is known, is very popular among school psychologists, since, in particular, it is designed for different age categories of schoolchildren. Its key feature is that, through the use of elements of the game, non-standard questions and constructive provocations, arouse in schoolchildren an active interest in their own professional self-determination, stimulate their readiness to perceive habitual phenomena in a non-standard way, meaningfully analyze their personal properties, obvious and hidden features of well-known professions. life values and established stereotypes of ideas about the existing being and their connection with a possible choice through their professional development.

The main theoretical and psychological foundations of vocational guidance in the context of the activities of a school psychologist include:

- 1) psychological aspects of the regulatory and legal framework of career guidance work, the psychological aspects of this work, the psychological foundations of professionography, taking into account the personal qualities of a person in the career guidance system;
- 2) the psychological component of information support for professional psychologists; socio-psychological dimension of schoolchildren's professional orientations; psychological bases of classification of professions; psychological bases for highlighting professionally important personal qualities of a specialist;
- 3) the psychological basis of the system of methods for implementing work with schoolchildren according to a comprehensive vocational guidance program: a psychological model of vocational guidance work at school, taking into account the coordination of the activities of teachers and practical psychologists acting as

school vocational consultants, psychological features of using forms and methods of vocational guidance work with people, psychological specifics activities with parents of optants, individual psychological parameters of schoolchildren's readiness for their professional self-determination;

4) psychological prerequisites for the formation of professional competence of school psychologists-professional consultants: a methodology for conducting preliminary psychological professional diagnostics, a scientifically based algorithm for conducting psychological professional consultations, the psychological foundations for the work of schoolchildren with professional materials, the psychological foundations for the use of adequate means of conducting career guidance activities, activating career guidance techniques.

The theoretical and psychological basis for the practical implementation of the career guidance work of a psychologist at school includes, in particular, a system of fundamental rules for its implementation by a school psychologist-professional consultant, which is summarized below.

1. To have complete knowledge of the professionograms of those professional specialties that are popular among students of a given school.
2. When conducting practical professional consultations, it is imperative to have indications and contraindications for the relevant professions, various methods of psychological and professional diagnostics, in order to be able to promptly implement the appropriate procedure, if necessary.
3. In the course of practical implementation of vocational counseling, actively promote the development of adequate self-esteem in schoolchildren, highlight appropriate positive personal qualities in them, and help them master the means of objective self-determination.
4. The proposed career guidance recommendations should be communicated to schoolchildren tactfully, and the very procedure of professional counseling should be carried out in a confidential environment. At the same time, their career

guidance efforts should be directed, taking into account the relevant professional needs and requirements of society.

5. A psychologist-professional consultant should strive to ask specific substantive questions during vocational counseling, summarizing and systematizing answers to them in the context of relevant career guidance goals, and giving his advice to schoolchildren, bear moral and professional responsibility for their consequences.

6. A school psychologist who conducts career guidance work with schoolchildren must be confident that each schoolchild, in particular a high school student, is a carrier of a relatively self-sufficient personality, characterized by unique individual interests, abilities, and other personal characteristics that must be taken into account in the realization of his potential.

7. A professional psychologist must exhaustively and comprehensively implement all appropriate psychodiagnostic examinations, help the student to realize his shortcomings, shortcomings and shortcomings, negative personal qualities, and also indicate in a confidential form the possibilities of their elimination.

8. The school psychologist draws conclusions about a particular student on the basis of a systematic, evidence-based study of his personality (recorded data from relevant observations, biographies, answers to questions from psychological questionnaires, medical diagnoses, and the results of a psychological test diagnosis).

9. A psychologist-professional consultant, influencing the intellectual and emotional spheres of the corresponding student, must constantly take into account his psychological state and constantly remember that among his goals is, in particular, to strive in every possible way to understand the counselor and be as clear as possible to them.

Conclusions. One of the defining components of any professionogram is the so-called psychogram, which includes a description of the actual “psychological” features of the profession. Each specific profession determines the requirements for the quantitative and qualitative expression of individual mental functions-

formations (sensation, perception, memory, thinking, imagination, speech, attention, will) in the subject of its implementation, their relationship and interaction during the deployment of this implementation, which necessitates the presence of certain personal-psychological abilities in such a subject. It is the psychogram that is designed to reflect this originality and make it clear to a person what requirements to his psyche, to his personality are put forward by the profession that arouses his interest.

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